

Prime-Generating Monic Cubic Polynomials – Search Report

This document summarizes the results of an extensive computational search over monic cubic polynomials of the form:

$$f(n) = n^3 + a \cdot n^2 + b \cdot n + c$$

The objective was to determine the longest sequence of consecutive prime values generated by $f(n)$ starting from $n = 0$.

Search Domain

$$a \in [-2000, 2000]$$

$$b \in [-2000, 2000]$$

$$c \in [2, 50000], \text{ with } c \text{ restricted to prime values.}$$

This corresponds to a total of over **82.169 billion** monic cubic polynomials tested.

Highest Run Length Found

The longest sequence of consecutive primes was:

$$L = 30$$

Generated by the polynomial:

$$f(n) = n^3 + 23n^2 - 1988n + 24223$$

This polynomial yields 30 consecutive prime values for $n = 0$ through $n = 29$.

Top 20 Polynomials (by run length L)

L	a	b	c
30	23	-1988	24223
29	-35	308	73
29	14	-1239	16111
29	26	-1939	22259
28	17	-1208	14887
28	63	-1978	14033
28	-32	241	347
28	29	-1884	20347
27	20	-1171	13697
27	-39	368	269
27	-29	180	557

27	32	-1823	18493
27	66	-1849	12119
26	328	-1225	16069
26	-36	293	599
26	25	-1332	15377
26	69	-1714	10337
26	35	-1756	16703
26	-26	125	709
26	23	-1128	12547

Conclusion

This computational exploration confirms that within the tested domain, the polynomial producing the longest prime run is:

$$f(n) = n^3 + 23n^2 - 1988n + 24223 \text{ with } L = 30.$$

All results were validated using deterministic primality testing. The dataset of all polynomials with $L \geq 10$ has been preserved for future analysis.